

Socio-Economic Status of Agriculture Labour in Nizamabad District

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Abstract:- Agriculture sector is the eminent source of income generation in the rural and some of urban areas in the part of sustainable development in India. Agriculture and its allied labour works are the major source of financially backward sections. Most of rural inhabitants of Telangana are depends upon agriculture labour to fulfill their financial needs. The status of all other developments are interlinked with agriculture labour because if they did not get the work in a particular day even they unable to feed their family. If the people get labour work regularly it may change the Socio- Economic status of the family. This research work assess about the socio-Economic status of agriculture labour in Nizamabad District.

Keywords:- 1.Socio-Economic Status 2.Agriculture Labour.

I. INTRODUCTION

Majority of the rural population profession is agriculture labour in Nizamabad District. In the three revenue divisions of Nizamabad district like Bhodan, Armour and Nizamabad have agriculture labour is their duty. In those divisions Armour Division is an icon for new agriculture activities and innovative methods. This area is also known as “The Rice Bowl of Telangana. In this area the labourers come from neighbor states for getting employment through agriculture. The life style of this division population was completely changed through the agriculture sector. The rural people of Nizamabad division gets their employment by agriculture marketing in this process they will get Agriculture related labour works in urban areas of Nizamabad District. In Bhodhan revenue Division most of the areas are highly backward areas the people of this division migrated to nearest agriculture areas for getting field work. This research work reveals the Socio-Economic Status of Nizamabad District.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

➤ *M. Radhakrishnaiah (2015):*

In this article” Socioeconomic Conditions of Agricultural Labour in Rayalaseema, Andhra Pradesh” he stated that nearly 70 % of the people are depends upon agriculture sector in India. Agriculture labour occupies a prominent role to shape the rural India. The majority of the agriculture labour is males. The people who are belongs to backward classes are doing agriculture labour in Andhrapradesh. The family size of majority agriculture is

Medium size. The majority of the agriculture labourers are illiterates in Andhrapradesh.

➤ *S. D. Dineshkumar(2017):*

In this article named”Socio–Economic Conditions of Women Agricultural Labourersin Cuddalore District” he stated that women agriculture labour plays a crucial role in crop production and economic activities of the family through the labour earnings. She also says that the age group of women labours is in between 20 to 40 years have engaged agriculture activities in Cuddalore. The highest labourers are unable to save their wages and they are earning 1000-2000 RS per Month. The majority of the labour unable to get day to day needs for their family.

➤ *Objectives of the Study:*

- To assess the status of agriculture Employment in Nizamabad District.
- To know the Socio-Economic Status of agriculture labour in Nizamabad District.
- To know the agriculture allied activities in Nizamabad District.

➤ *Area of the Study:*

I have selected Three Revenue Divisions in Nizamabad District for this research work.

III. METHODOLOGY

Survey method is implemented for this research work to meet objectives of the study. Primary data is collected through the questionnaire and secondary data is also collected by other source in the part of research.

Chart 1 Gender

This Pie- Chart Shows that majority of the respondents are females who are doing agriculture labour in Nizamabad District that is with 80%. The remaining respondents are males that are 20% are doing agriculture labour for their family feeding including in rural and urban areas of Nizamabad District.

Chart 2 Education Qualification

This Pie –Chart reveals that the highest percent of the respondents are illiterates that are 90% who are elected agriculture labour for their family sustainability. The very less percentage that is 10% of the respondents are educated in Nizamabad District. The people who are educated they are limited to Primary and Secondary levels because of their Socio-Economic conditions and their own interest on the education.

Chart 3 Social Category

Majority of the agriculture labour is from backward class (BC) that is 60% .Next place occupied by schedule caste (SC) with 20%, other category labours are in the next line with 10 % that is Schedule Tribes (ST) and remaining respondents are limited to only 5%.The above Pie-Chart-3 concludes that the division of the social category is depicts the highest agriculture labour comes from Backward Classes in Nizamabad District.

Chart 4 AgricultureLand

The Pie-Chart 4 shows that the majority of the agriculture labour who are living in Nizamabad District are do not have their own agriculture land with 92%. The very less percent of the respondents have their own land to get income through agriculture activities. This Chart concludes that the majority of the agriculture labour are land less people in Nizamabad District.

Chart 5 Employment Through Agriculture

The highest respondents are getting employment through the agriculture and its relevant activities for their economical sustain with 74 % in Nizamabad District. The next place occupied by the respondents who are in neutral with the above statement that is 16%. Only 10% of the respondents are said that they did not getting employment through the agriculture and its other related activities in Nizamabad District.

Chart 6 Agriculture Work

The Pie-Chart 6 explains that most of the respondents that is 85% are getting labour in the rural areas of Nizamabad District for their family feeding. Only 15 % of the respondents getting labour work in the urban areas of Nizamabad District. This chart concludes that the rural areas are the agriculture labour hubs in Nizamabad District.

Table 1 How Many Years your being an Agriculture Labour

Value Label	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 Years	08	04.00
5-10 Years	10	05.00
11-15 Years	10	05.00
16-20 Years	52	26.00
21 years and above	120	60.00
	200	100.00

Table 1 Depicts that the experience wise categorization most of the respondents have above 21 years of experience in agriculture labour work that is 60%. Only 8% of the respondents limited to less than 5 years of experience in Nizamabad.

Table 2 Type of Labour in Agriculture

Value Label	Frequency	Percent
Daily	170	85.00
Weekly	12	06.00
Monthly	10	05.00
Half yearly	04	02.00
Yearly	04	02.00
	200	100.00

There were 85% of the respondents are getting Daily labour. The respondents who are working for yearly and Half Yearly contact base that is 4% this is the very least percentage among them. This Table concludes that most of the laborers are willing to do Daily labour in Nizamabad District.

Table 3 Per Annum how Much Income you are Getting

Value Label	Frequency	Percent
1 to 10K	06	03.00
11 to 20K	14	07.00
20 to 30K	150	75.00
30 to 40K	08	04.00
Above 40K	22	11.00
	200	100.00

Table 3 Points out that the 75% of the respondents are getting income 20 to 30 K per year. The very limited number of respondents is getting 1 to 10 Thousands of income per annum. This Table concludes that the income of the respondent through agriculture labour is too less per year if we compare with other professions.

Table 4 Economical Status of your Family

Value Label	Frequency	Percent
below Poverty Line	170	85.00
above Poverty Line	12	06.00
Elite	08	04.00
Any other	10	05.00
	200	100.00

Table 4 finds out that the majority of the respondents who are doing agriculture labour belongs to Below Poverty Line with 85%. The very least percentage of the respondents is Elite Family who is opted agriculture labour is their profession.

Table 5 Nature of Labour

Value Label	Frequency	Percent
Planting	160	80.00
Seed Processing	12	06.00
Cutting	08	04.00
Cultivation	16	08.00
Other source	04	02.00
	200	100.00

This table 5 explains that the respondents are doing plantation work with 80%. The least percent of the respondents are depends upon the other source of agriculture labour that is 2%.

IV. CONCLUSION

This research paper find out that women are in the front line than Men in doing agriculture labour work. Backward class people are depends upon agriculture labour work because most of the BC communities in Nizamabad are considered agriculture labour is their own profession. A large number of illiterate people are fixed to agriculture labour in rural areas because it is one and only large employment source for illiterate people in Nizamabad District, and also the educated people are limited to Primary and Secondary levels because the Socio-Economic conditions of that families are not permitted to them for higher studies. The 70% of the labourers in three divisions

are considered agriculture labour is their profession. The residents of rural areas are uneducated and unskilled so they are depends on agriculture sector for employment. Agriculture labour is the available income source and they are unable to divert other profession that is why they are stick to daily labour work. The land fewer personalities of rural areas are depends upon agriculture related works for feeding their families. The annual income range is too less this factor pull them into backward socially and economically in Nizamabad District.

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